

TerraDT

D 5.1

Architecture for interactive UI

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D5.1 - Architecture for interactive UI

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application programming interface
DestinE	Destination Earth
DEDL	Destination Earth Data Lake
DESP	Destination Earth Service Platform
DT	Digital Twin
HDA	Harmonised Data Access
HPC	High-performance computing
ML	Machine learning
PoC	Proof of Concept
REST	Representational State Transfer
UI	User interface

Keywords

Digital Twin; Impact model; User interface; Destination Earth Service Platform

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the foundations of design and architecture for the map-based interactive UI (user interface) to be developed in the TerraDT WP6 and generalization of the design in WP7. Moreover, it showcases the relevant selected technologies used in development. Additionally, it describes the platforms used in development and where the UI will be integrated into. Furthermore, it establishes the data sources and formats needed and used by the UI. Finally, it presents use cases for the sea ice impact model and the urban and carbon impact model.

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1. Introduction

As climate change progresses, enhancing our understanding of its impacts becomes increasingly crucial. Specifically, detailed insights into the regional and local impacts of climate change are essential to inform and guide adaptation and mitigation strategies effectively. The goal of the Destination Earth (DestinE) initiative is to respond to this need by developing Digital Twins (DTs) that can provide accurate information on environmental changes and support decision making. The basis of TerraDT is a modular infrastructure with a generic coupling interface that allows expanding the DestinE DTs by flexibly adding new components, or replacing them with advanced versions or emulators based on artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML). TerraDT will also develop impact models which provide user-relevant and actionable information, including applications with interactive capabilities. **TerraDT will improve the reliability and relevance of the climate projections and impact assessments of DestinE which is critical for users planning adaptation and mitigation actions.**

As part of climate change impact and mitigation measures assessment, it is crucial for researchers to be able to investigate the impact of climate change adaptation measures effectively. This document aims to describe overall architecture for an interactive user interface with which a user can modify the impact model input and see the results of different scenarios. More in detail, the user will be able to view results as a map and graphs over selected time frames. **Users** in this case would be researchers, city planners, engineers, and professionals in such fields working with various planning tasks where adaptation to climate change has a key role. This user interface is not a tool for the user to apply their own tools; neither is it a platform for data manipulation outside beforehand defined actions, but will allow users to assess and examine different climate scenarios with pre-defined changeable parameters.

The novel approach we aim to build is to integrate high-performance computing (HPC) with map-based user interface for those use cases where it is relevant to calculate results over several map tiles. Often it is so that environmental changes and mitigation actions require calculating and viewing results over geographically vast areas - meanwhile in user interfaces it is desirable to return results fast for users to investigate. In addition, we want to do it with relatively fine spatial resolution. We aim to tackle adjusting these needs with this architecture and selection of technologies in a meaningful way.

The impact models in question are sea ice impact model, carbon sequestration model and urban land use model. Our pilot study areas are the Gulf of Riga (for sea ice) and cities of Lisbon and Helsinki (for land use and carbon models). We aim to build a **proof of concept** (PoC) that can later be scaled to larger areas and for different models if needed. We are aware that this approach - design during the first months and building software later - should be open for change as software is better designed in an agile way. This document does not aim to be a final solution that dictates the work for coming years. Instead, this document aims to describe basic architecture but it leaves room for emerging technologies and agile methods in the developing process.

The actual **use case descriptions** are written in Annex 1: Use Case Descriptions.

2. User interface

The main goal of the UI is for the user to be able to interact with the urban, carbon and sea ice impact models. Other parts of the UI are designed to be as clear and concise as possible to support this goal. With this interface, the user will be able to see how changes in the given variables affect the model outputs. The variables and outputs are explained as concisely as possible by the UI, so the user understands what they are affecting.

The architecture and the dataflow of the UI is presented in Figure 1, with the open-ended arrows signifying flow of the application and the closed arrows communication and requests. The different protocols which are used for the communications are indicated in each of the communication arrows. Most of the communication is done via Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) requests, with the exception being the HPC API which communicates with the HPC via Secure Shell Protocol (SSH) and Secure Copy Protocol (SCP).

2.1. Functionality

The impact model interfaces will contain a map section which will be used to visualize the outputs from the impact models as well as a selection interface. In addition to the geographical area and/or point selection, there will be a section for other relevant variables which will change depending on the impact model. The impact model results are calculated when the needed variables are given and the submit button is pressed. When the impact model results are complete, they will be shown in the map interface as well as in an accompanying output section. This output section will be in the same view as the map section so that they could be analyzed simultaneously.

2.2. Front-end

The front-end of the UI is implemented utilizing Vue.js as the main JavaScript framework with the addition of OpenLayers for the map elements. Utilizing Vue.js helps to add possible components later in the UIs lifecycle. OpenLayers provides the ability to add an open-source dynamic map to the UI with a diverse set of features. Tailwind CSS is used to stylize the interface.

The front-end is split into an info page and the map interfaces. The info page will provide information on the impact models, the corresponding partner organizations, and the UI itself. The impact model interfaces will be in their own tabs which are accessible from the header as well as from their corresponding info page section.

The front-end sends the input variables given by the user to the back-end and waits for the back-end to respond with the results from the model calculations.

Figure 1 – User Interface architecture

2.3. Back-end

The back-end of the UI is made using a Python framework named Flask to make the model calculations, which are coded in Python, as seamless as possible. Flask is lightweight and easy to set up, which is beneficial for the PoC UI, but also provides the ability to scale in the future. The back-end is split into separate containerized sections for better scalability and resilience.

The back-end architecture is described in Figure 2. The front-end communicates with the request handling part which carries the parameters forward to the data processing part. This then communicates with the DestinE Data Lake (DEDL) and the temporary Network File System (NFS) inside the node which is cloned from the persistent NFS. Relevant data is carried through to the model calculation part of the back-end.

2.3.1. Model calculation

The model results are calculated on the back-end when the front-end sends a request with the given input parameters. Lightweight and moderate calculations, which only need reasonable computing time in an interface context, can be done on the node itself. These results are then sent back to the front-end for the user to interact with.

2.3.2. Data processing

The back-end needs relevant data for the selected area in order to calculate the impact model results. The integral model data is cloned from a persistent storage into the node when the node is started. The selected area data to be processed is downloaded into the back-end using HTTP requests pointing to the REST API endpoint.

Figure 2 – Back-end architecture

2.4. HPC API

In general, HPC-as-a-Service concept provides remote and secure access to high-performance computing resources in a service-like manner. Prespecified model calculations with given parameters from the UI can be run on HPC utilizing the HEAppE Middleware. HEAppE is IT4Innovations' in-house implementation of HPC-as-a-Service concept. HEAppE manages and provides information about submitted and running jobs in the batch scheduler and their data between the client application and the HPC infrastructure. HEAppE is able to submit required computation or simulation on HPC infrastructure, monitor the progress and notify the user. It provides necessary functions for job management, monitoring and reporting, user authentication and authorisation, file transfer, encryption, and various notification mechanisms.

HEAppE can submit and run jobs in an HPC environment without the requester directly interfacing the HPC themselves. The back-end of the UI communicates with HEAppE through its REST API. In order for the back-end to know when the job is finished, it needs to query the HEAppE API in regular intervals.

3. Platform

The UI is designed to be containerized and thus be able to be placed in a container orchestration system, which provides automation for scaling, management, and deployment. The PoC UI will be developed utilizing CSC Rahti service as the ability to develop inside the Destination Earth Service Platform (DESP) is not possible at the moment. Afterwards, the UI will be integrated into DESP which has its own container orchestration system.

During the development phase, the UI will have a dummy login page with a demo account which acts as an Identity Access Management (IAM) tool for that phase. When integrating into DESP, the UI will use the DESP IAM for regulating access.

3.1. Destination Earth Service Platform - DESP

As the UI will be integrated into DESP in the final part of the project, it needs to be designed with the platform in mind. The UI needs to be deployable using a Kubernetes package manager Helm. Additionally, it needs to support Kubernetes features such as replica Pods and Horizontal Pod Autoscaling. The credentials and/or certificate keys utilized by the UI need to be set using Kubernetes Secrets.

4. Data

Utilizing and processing data correctly is one of the most important aspects of the UI. In order to calculate the impact model results, the UI back-end needs the resulting predictions from the climate model calculations. These model results are precalculated. As a backup strategy for demonstration purposes, the UI will have pre-downloaded data of certain areas to ensure the UI can function correctly if data sources are not responsive.

4.1. Data sources

Data utilized in the UI is requested from the DestinE Data Lake (DEDL) into the node by the back-end when it is needed. The DEDL requires an Authentication Token when requesting data from its services.

4.2. Data formats

As the back-end is made with Python, the data preferably is in a format that is easily processed with the Python data processing library pandas. The data that is available on Harmonised Data Access (HDA) is in the Zarr data format which is designed to be usable with cloud computing and the data can be split into more easily digestible chunks. Another possible data format usable with pandas is the Network Common Data Form (NetCDF) which is widely used in climatology, meteorology, and oceanography.

Annex 1: Use case descriptions

Use cases for sea ice impact model

We aim to define the steps needed to produce maps required by engineers when designing ship routes and wind farms. This requires information on the regional variability of parameters relevant for construction durability and strength calculations, such as sea ice probability, maximum thickness, and ice drift. Engineers typically rely on statistical curves to design structures that can withstand extreme values over long lifetimes of 50, 100, or even 500 years. As records do not cover such long return periods or future extremes, fitted statistical models of sea ice parameters must be applied.

- ❖ Step 1: Plotting a gridded map of sea ice variability, both seasonal and interannual, provides first-order information for engineers. This allows them to identify which ice-related aspects must be considered in planning. Users can define a region of interest and obtain a full climatology of ice conditions for that location where infrastructure is planned. User should be able to:
 - ◆ Select a geographic area and time frame
 - ◆ Calculate sea ice thickness, probability, and ice season length based on model results for past and future climate scenarios
 - ◆ View sea ice thickness and probability for the selected area and user-defined thresholds (for example, probability of ice thickness > 1 m) as maps and graphs (Fig. A1.1b, Fig. A1.2a)

Figure A1.1. Data examination: a) subregion selection (Gulf of Riga in this example), b) map of selected ice parameter climatological distribution, c) time series of the selected parameter at the location marked in panel b.

Figure A1.2. Climatology model for regional sea ice state: a) filtered sea ice statistics map showing annual mean thickness of packed ice (concentration > 0.7), b) seasonal ice coverage for the selected region with season start and end statistics, c) time series of annual maximum sea ice thickness at the selected location/area, d) comparison and bias correction for sea ice thickness.

❖ Step 2: Gridded map of sea ice climatological statistics with correction methods

User should be able to:

- ◆ select geographic area and time frame (Step 1)
 - View sea ice climatology and relevant temporal statistics (Fig A1.2b)
 - Extract block maxima for defined periods (annual or monthly), for example annual maximum sea ice thickness for a selected location or area (Fig. A1.2c)
- ◆ Apply thresholds for sea ice parameters to filter relevant conditions, for example calculate statistics (e.g. maximum) for ice parameters (e.g. ice thickness) for packed ice conditions (e.g. concentration > 0.7) (Fig. A1.2a)
- ◆ Perform first-order bias correction ($a \cdot X + b$) of sea ice thickness using observational data (Fig. A1.2d)

Figure A1.3. General Extreme Value (GEV) model applied to sea ice thickness at the selected location/area: a) annual maximum sea ice thickness (blue dots) and GEV fit (red line), b) GEV return level plot with 95% confidence interval as uncertainty, c) map of return values with shaded uncertainty.

- ❖ Step 3: Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) analysis. User should be able to:
 - ◆ Select a geographic area and time frame (as in Step 1) and fit a GEV distribution for the chosen location (Fig. A1.3a)
 - ◆ Estimate the uncertainty of the GEV fit (Fig. A1.3b) and select the return period of interest
 - ◆ Generate a map of return values per-grid-cell (for defined return period) with shaded regions indicating uncertainty (Fig. A1.3c)

Use cases for urban and carbon impact model

As climate change intensifies, the ability to measure carbon emissions and capture, alongside understanding how humans and ecosystems are exposed to extreme weather, is becoming central to societal resilience. Urban development choices—such as the use of heat-absorbing materials and the decline of vegetation—worsen climate extremes by fuelling the Urban Heat Island effect, which not only disrupts local carbon cycles but also alters climate patterns. To mitigate and adapt to these challenges effectively, cities require precise predictions of urban carbon cycles and temperature dynamics that account for land use changes and localised heat effects. The urban impact model responds to this need through two complementary components: one that quantifies urban carbon sequestration and another that evaluates the impacts of climate extremes. Together, they measure urban carbon capture, map areas vulnerable to heat stress, and test the role of nature-based solutions in regulating temperature and enhancing carbon storage under both current and projected climate conditions. By integrating these capabilities into an interactive interface, it equips city planners with the maps, statistics, and projections they need to guide urban design and policy. To put these features into practice, the idea is to offer planners a set of interactive tools that connect model outputs with decision-making needs. Specifically, users will be able to:

- ❖ Plot a gridded map showing extreme values for temperature. Users can change land use land cover schemes to see what would be the variation in near-surface air temperature as a function of new parks or new buildings (i.e. Figure A1.4). For this the climate model would be pre-defined. User should be able to:
 - ◆ Select geographic area and time frame
 - ◆ Modify land use class in the map grid with 200m x 200m cells
 - ◆ Select a pre-trained climate projection scenario
 - ◆ Run the climate model to calculate the temperature outcome for a single time step
 - ◆ View statistics from temperature maps as graphs
- ❖ Plot a gridded map showing carbon sequestration over a city, 50m x 50m grid cells
 - ◆ Select geographic area and time frame
 - ◆ Modify land use class in the map grid, 200m x 200m cells
 - ◆ Select a pre-trained model to calculate carbon sequestration for grid cells
 - ◆ View and plot statistics from carbon sequestration maps as graphs (i.e. Figure A1.5)

Figure A1.4. Air temperature (T_a) model predictions for the 'Denser City' under a 'Future HW day' scenario, and T_a differences to an equivalent 'Current City' scenario: (a-b) nocturnal median (UTS Stage 1, from 11 p.m. to 6 a.m.); and (c-d) late afternoon maximum (UTS Stage 5, from 6 p.m. to 8 p.m.). (Oliveira et al., 2021)

Figure A1.5. Carbon fluxes of urban habitats in the Helsinki area at 50x50 m resolution: simulated with a process-based ecosystem model (left column); emulator derived (middle column); and relative difference between ecosystem model and emulator fluxes (right column). Top row: Annual average Gross Primary Production (GPP). Bottom row: Annual average Net Ecosystem Exchange (NEE).

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